

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

BB-4312

ORGANISATION DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE

MULTIPLE CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

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Submission date: 5 May 2020

Abstract:

This paper aims to analyse the case study of the three organisation namely: Brutel, Sumbiling Eco Village, and Society for Community Outreach and Training in regards to sustainable management organisation. Problems/symptoms and their root cause for each organisation will be identified based on the challenges that they are facing, and recommended organisation development intervention will be provided.

The context for analysis:

This section will explore the concept of the Sustainable Management Organisation to provide context for the analysis for each of the three organisation, as discussed by Cummings and Worley (2015).

Sustainable Management Organisation (SMO) is a relatively new type of intervention in Organisational development and change. The central purpose of this intervention is to help organisations achieve and maintain sustainable effectiveness, in all three important aspects namely; positive economic, environmental, and social results. To achieve its purpose, this intervention provides strategy, design, and guidelines for the organisations. In addition, other interventions in organisational development might be needed to achieve sustainability.

In Cummings and Worley (2015), the author provided organisation design guidelines as well as the application stages in SMO. The design guideline contains discussions about the strategy, objectives. Identity and agile organisational design that supports sustainable effectiveness. Application stages touch on the aspect of implementation from identifying/ redefining organisation identity, repurposing Boards of Directors, building capabilities, and finally sequencing of change.

Brutel, Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV), and Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT) will be analysed as an organisation that practices sustainability. Once the problem has been identified, other relevant interventions in organisation development and change will be recommended for each organisation based on the information available in their case study respectively. The recommended intervention is aimed to improve its position as a sustainable organisation.

The analysis for each organisation starts with identifying the problems/symptoms that they are currently facing as a sustainable organisation. Followed by the root cause of the problem/symptoms. Next, the case analysis will be done to assess their situation as an organisation that practices SMO. From there, solutions that are relevant to the organisation situation as an organisation that practice SMO and the root problems that the organisation is currently facing will be provided. Finally, the recommendation of intervention that is the most appropriate will be suggested.

Brutel:

Problem:

implementing paperless might led to Brutel losing some of its customer segment, in particular, the elderly

Root problem:

the elderly have a hard time accepting the new paperless system because

1. They might forget to pay their bills, as the paper act as a reminder
2. They might forget their password due to password fatigue
3. The enrolment process can be cumbersome. First, they are not interested. And next, if the process is complex, they might give up halfway.

Case analysis:

The company seems to have good objectives to support sustainable effectiveness. The company is well established, they seem to have a good economic performance which allows them to invest in other social and environmental activities for corporate social responsibilities to comply with Brunei vision 2035. amongst the four goals that they have set; education, art & culture, environment, and finally entrepreneurship, they give the highest emphasis on the environmental aspect. They are committed to environmental practices and policies, and further support this aspect by educating Bruneian in a friendly way.

Currently, according to Jamilah Kassim, the Communication and Media Manager, the company is undergoing the implementation of more green initiatives, in particular, the transition from paper-based to paperless. This provides them with the opportunity to improve their corporate social responsibilities and at the same time, reducing their operating cost. However, they are faced with the problem of losing their customer segment, in particular, the elderly as the elderly might have a hard time to accept the new system.

In the current phase, they are doing marketing to promote the benefits of going paperless and in addition, it is also important to note that they have already implemented the paperless initiative and combining it with other benefits such as sending money abroad, through the use of their E-wallet system to further attract people to adopt the paperless system. However, they planned to develop strategies or implement action to overcome its challenges in regards to the elderly once they can remove the hesitation customer have especially the elderly to adopt paperless, through their marketing practices. From here we can assume that once marketing can be considered successful. They will either

1. Still in the process of developing strategies, or
2. Start implementing action.

It seems to suggest that the current situation, while marketing is being done, they are already developing strategies on how to deal with the problem, but they are not sure whether they will be able to get it ready by the end of the marketing session.

Marketing without having a tangible action to support that marketing can lead to a bad reputation (Cummings & Worley, 2015). They have mentioned "convenience" in the marketing section which aims for elderly people, but they are still in progress to ensure that they will be able to provide that convenience. Considering the problem, convenience for the elderly here would mean, a system that can help them remember their password, having a proper reminder system, and a simple enrolment process.

They will lose their customers if, during the period of marketing, some of the elderly tried enrolling in the e-bill system. There is no reason provided why they have taken such actions. Plausible reasons are flawed decision making in managing change, or factors that lead to the situation whereby they have to continue their marketing while their fixes have yet to be done. Perhaps due to inability of the members involved in finishing the fixes on time, or perhaps resources problems, etc. Therefore, they are lacking in the aspect of building capabilities for change in SMO design principle in particular change capability (Cummings & Worley, 2015). However, in the current situation, they need to ensure that the solution to ensure an elderly smooth transition to paperless will be finished as soon as possible. This will help increase the chances of success of the transition to paperless for the elderly.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experienced CEO - Good infrastructure with over 500 employees and 10 retail branches - Sustainable organization in economic, environmental and social 	-
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of operating cost by going paperless - increase brand positive identity through paperless 	-

Solutions:

Process consultation:

"the creation of a relationship that permits the client to perceive, understand and act on the process events that occur in [his or her] internal and external environment in order to improve the situation as defined by the client" (Cummings & Worley, 2015). The consultant will not provide expert help or solutions to the clients, instead, they help the client to assess and improve human processes such as communication, interpersonal relations, decision making, and task performance. To ensure effectiveness, the consultant and manager should be a good helper to aid others in getting tasks done and to achieve their goals. This intervention is more of a philosophy that ensures the client

receiving the help, gain the necessary skill to ensure the effective diagnosis of the problem so that they will be able to solve it by themselves. In addition, process consultation also provides group intervention to provide the same skills to allow group members to solve their problems.

Team building:

According to Cummings and Worley (2015) team is a group of people who relied upon each other to achieve a common purpose, using a common work method and hold each other accountable. Team building intervention which is also known as team development is a broad range of planned activities that will help the team improve their ways of accomplishing the task, enhancing their interpersonal and problem-solving skills and generally, improve team performances. There are many types of teams such as permanent workgroups, temporary project teams, and virtual teams. Through this intervention, it will allow the team to fully maximise their use of members resources and contribution. Furthermore, it is also used as a supplement or to facilitate other Organisation development interventions.

According to Tannenbaum, Beard, and Salas (1992) there are many factors that influence team performance. Starting with the organisational characteristic such as reward system, resource scarcity, organisational climate, and many more. Factors that are internal to the team are task characteristic which relates to task difficulty, work structure which refer to how work is assigned, who the member should report to, individual characteristic relates the ability of the each of the member and team characteristic which refers to team cohesiveness and reflection of a sense of belonging. These four internal factors will further influence team processes such as communication and decision making and ultimately influence team performance.

Next, there are four major approaches to team building namely the goal-setting approach, interpersonal approach, role approach, and finally problem-solving approach. However, it is important to note that team building intervention can consist of a hybrid between the four approaches depending on the diagnosis of the team situation (Tannenbaum, Beard & Salas, 1992). In addition, according to Cummings and Worley (2015), confusion can happen between process consultation and team-building intervention. Process consultation is more focused on helping relationships and more general compared to team building where it involves improving how the task is being performed. Furthermore, process consultation is usually included inside team-building intervention.

Finally, team building is considered to be very important, considering the challenges managements faces with regards to complexity and uncertainty in fast-paced industry such as software and hard development (Cummings & Worley, 2015).

Change management training:

According to Cummings and Worley (2015), there are 5 five key elements in ensuring effective change management. The five key elements are; motivating change which includes creating readiness for change and overcoming the resistance to change, followed by creating a visioning process to describe the core ideology and constructing the envisioned future, next developing political support includes process such as assessing the change agent power, identifying the key

stakeholders and influencing stakeholders, managing the transition which involves activity planning, commitment planning, and management structure, and finally, sustaining momentum, includes providing resources for change, building a support system for change agents, developing new competencies and skills, reinforcing new behaviors and staying on the course.

A training program can be developed to provide the existing relevant employees with the necessary skills to increase their effectiveness in managing change.

Recommendation:

From the analysis, they do need improvement in how they are managing the change, in particular the sequence of activities such as marketing. This can be done through Change management training. However, having the training right now would be too late considering that the damage is already done. Considering the situation in the case study, the problem with their approach is small in comparison to the scope of change management and there are no problems mentioned in other parts in the process of organisation change from paper-based to paperless. Therefore, it is not practical to conduct it in this situation. However, the mistakes that they have made can be reflected upon for future improvement to increase their change capability.

Considering the current situation, they should opt for team building intervention or process consultation, both will help improve the team decision making in solving the problem related to the elderly. However, it is hard to pinpoint which intervention suits better considering that there is missing information on why they have yet to finish preparing the fix for the problem that they are facing. However, keeping in the mind the limited information provided and the customer segment that is involved in the problem is elderly, team-building will be better in comparison to process consultation. According to Cummings and Worley (2015), the decision-making process needs to include non-traditional stakeholders, in this case, the elderly, which will be able to provide perspectives relevant to the problem. Through team-building intervention, the team that is responsible in solving the problem, not only can improve their processes to ensure that they can achieve their objective fast, but develop trust with the elderly that can provide perspectives for them, which is another factor that can help them achieve their objective.

Sumbiling Eco Village:

Problems:

SEV is facing difficulties in enhancing its product and services as well as to maintain and sustain its mission and vision. Furthermore, they also have nearby competitors that might be able to provide a more innovative and sustainable activity that are more attractive to tourist, local and foreign workers, in comparison to SEV. Furthermore, SEV over-dependence on tourism is very risky as many external factors such as fluctuation in climate, currency exchange rate, and political and social conditions will affect the business operations. All of this highlights the importance of having enough expertise in the industry to ensure they can enhance their product and services, maintain and sustain mission and vision and finally to encourage more innovation in their activities to attract customer and to ensure that they can come up with alternatives activities to reduce their dependencies on tourism.

Root Problem:

Ecotourism is a relatively new way of doing tourism in Brunei leading to skill shortages.

Case analysis:

Unlike Brutel who slowly improved their practices in terms of sustainability of economic, environmental, and social, SEV is a social enterprise in the industry of ecotourism, and the owner, Leslie Chiang was a pioneer in community-based tourism. Therefore, from early on, the company has already included the three objectives in SMO which are economic, environmental, and social. Through the Eco village, not only environments were conserved, but the community also benefit through the preservation of valuable knowledge, boosting the community's self-esteem and improving their economic gain. However, the organisation emphasizes that without proper planning and management, the company runs the risk of environmental degradation as well as affecting the community culture, the two aspects that they wished to conserve.

Currently, they are still lacking in one of the important aspects of SMO, which is talent management. Considering their inability to achieve their current need is related to the talent shortage, they need to find ways to hire more talents while ensuring that their current human resource capital is retained. Otherwise, they will not be able to enhance their product and services, maintain and sustain their mission and vision as well as innovate to compete with other competitors.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
- Sustainable organization in economic, environmental and social	- Economic resources require them to give up on some green aspect
Opportunities	Threats
- Green building concept might increase market share while ensuring sustainability	- Skill shortages in ecotourism in Brunei

Solutions:

Recruitment and selection through social media:

According to Forbes (2017), finding talents through social media and online job sites is one of the five talent management tactics when there is a skill shortage. Social media is especially relevant in finding young job-seekers around 18- to 34-year-olds, whereby 73% of job-seekers around that age manage to get recruited through social networking sites (Beard, 2015, as cited by Wilkinson, Redman & Dundon, 2017). According to Wilkinson, Redman and Dundon (2017), One way, whereby companies use social media to recruit job-seekers are called 'viral recruitment' a trend where the company uses social media to target job-seekers that is technologically literate. For example, is through publicizing a recruitment campaign that revolves around cybersecurity which requires potential talents to play games to crack a cryptic code. Although such methods of recruitment are more exposed in the other part of the world, it will be a potential method that can be used in Brunei in the future, considering that 94% of Bruneian is using social media in 2019 (Statista, 2020).

Career Planning and Development Intervention:

According to Cummings and Worley (2015), Career planning and development is very important and organisation has been pressured clarify this aspect. This is because of organisation increasing reliance on "intellectual capital", the war for talent, and increasing knowledge-based strategies. Furthermore, career planning and development intervention are considered to be a crucial tool in ensuring the development and retention of an effective workforce. This is further supported by the increasing trends of employees becoming more and more active in planning and managing their careers.

Career planning and development intervention will be able to provide an organisation with the appropriate resources, tools, and processes that are crucial to help members of the organisation to plan and attain their career objectives. Career planning revolves around choosing jobs and occupations while career development focuses on helping employees to achieve their career objectives.

Next, there are four career stages namely: the establishment age where people are dependent on their higher-ups to explore possibilities and learning their capabilities, the advancement stage where employees are focusing in achieving and advancing their career choice and require less

guidance, the maintenance stage where employee focus is now on ensuring that they can maintain their success, and finally withdrawal stage concerning the final phase where the employee will leave their career. By diagnosing and understanding each stage, problems can be identified and interventions such as a workshop, developmental materials can be used to improve employee's career planning and development.

One of the sub-interventions under career development is the developmental training which is one of the oldest interventions in organisation development and change. This intervention will be able to provide workers with the knowledge, skills, and ability that are required to perform tasks. This intervention usually involves human resource development to conduct need assessment in three levels which are an organisation, task, and person analysis, followed by designing the training program, implementing it, and finally evaluating it. Over the years, the methods for training have broadened from classroom methods to computer-based which includes simulations, case studies, role play, and many more. This intervention can be conducted for employees of all career stages and it can also include heavy investment in education to help employees obtain a Degree.

Recommendation:

Although career development can help retain its talent to prevent the problem from becoming more intense, retention and turnover rate information was not shared in the case study. Therefore, it is safe to assume that, employee retention has yet to be problematic. Therefore, organisation should focus its effort on hiring more expertise, considering the limited supply of talents, Sumbiling Eco Village will be competing with other ecotourism company. In addition, while improving the hiring and recruitment process, the company can consider one intervention under career development, which is developmental training considering that Leslie Chiang intends to achieve sustainability through green building. Some developmental training requires sending the employee to gain a Degree. However, taking into account that the company is struggling with resources as mentioned earlier whereby it has to use other non-green material to save money, sending the employee to gain a degree might not be practical. Therefore, they can consider finding cheaper short courses related to green buildings to ensure that they have the expertise to develop the project.

SCOT:

Problem:

SCOT faces challenges in sustaining their financial funds. It has to rely on sponsorship and the public to carry out its program in the long term, and its day-to-day operation. Furthermore, the source of funds from outside the country has complications obtain. However, even inside Brunei, financial aid is not very often experienced, rather, other parties usually help them by providing facilities and technical aspects that they required. In an attempt to improve their financial condition, they have developed 2 projects namely; Youth against Poverty workshop and Green exchange Project.

Green Exchange Project, is a two-way exchange between the public and SCOT. The public provides recyclable material and traded it with a coupon provided by SCOT. By exchanging recyclable items, the public will receive commodities such as rice. This project provides the most fund and in 2016 alone, the Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) managed to obtained 3060\$ from the conversion of the 3060 kg recyclables. According to Anwar, the founder, this project is able to generate funds without any hassle. However, this project itself faces three problems; volatility prices of food, the possibility of lowered recycling rates, and manpower needed to do the project on a large scale. Although these problems have been addressed through increasing varieties of exchanges and social media publicity to increase manpower, it is still subject to environmental uncertainty, in particular, volunteer participation and the availability of recyclable materials. Therefore, Anwar needs to consider other initiatives for financial sustainability.

Root problem:

SCOT lack activities that can provide them with a stable source of funds internally.

Although they have managed to develop 2 projects that provide them with the sources of funds they required. It is highly dependent on public participation and the availability of recyclable materials.

Case analysis:

In terms of Objectives for sustainable outcomes, although they have struggled previously in the aspect of economic results, they have improved their coping ability to sustain their activities through developing and carrying out two projects which are Youth against Poverty Workshop and Green Exchange Project. Furthermore, although their main aim in the NGO is to alleviate poverty in Brunei, it has included environmental aspects in its operation. One activity that involves the environmental aspect is the Green exchange project which provides them with the most fund. Therefore, they did a great job of ensuring equality in objectives for sustainability. In the case study, Anwar is considering, whether or not to start new initiatives to ensure financial sustainability, considering that is the aspect that they are struggling since the beginning of time. According to Cummings and Worley (2015), the organisation needs to produce a positive

economic outcome to ensure survivability and reject profit-maximizing goals. Considering the current situation, their finances can be said to be enough to survive with help from the green exchange project. However, it is still subject to an uncertain environment in particular participation from the public, availability of recyclable and price volatility for both the food and recyclable rate. Therefore, they should consider new initiatives, not necessarily to implement it immediately but to prepare them for future changes.

In an attempt to find more new initiatives, they should consider the three strategies to support sustainability; breadth, aggressiveness, and differentiation (Cummings & Worley, 2015). Breadth concerning the balance of creating a more complex organisation and the carbon footprint or the social impact it might cause. Aggressiveness relates to a growth strategy that should be reasonable. Finally, differentiation strategy, that is activities that can reflect all of three outcomes.

To do this without interrupting their operation, SCOT should ensure that its work system is able to provide two types of work; core and exploitative, and creative, and exploratory (Cummings & Worley, 2015). Core and exploitative work should support the NGO's current strategic intents. It should also be reliable, predictable, and efficient while ensuring practicality. In the context of SCOT, through the core and exploitative work design, they can continuously improve their current operation, in particular, the Green Exchange Program. Creative and Exploratory work, on the other hand, allows the organisation to venture to new projects and to innovate, to ensure that they are able to produce positive economic in the case where Green Exchange will not be able to provide them with the funds they needed in the future. The team should be produced to venture into the creation of new initiatives.

SWOT analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovative - Sustainable organization in economic, environmental and social - Association members have expertise and skills to help with organization activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over-dependence on third parties to generate its funds
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Price volatility for commodities such as rice - Possibility of a lower recycling rate will affect their funds

Recommendation:

Management and Leadership Development intervention:

According to Cummings and Worley (2015), Management and Leadership Development intervention Is one of the very well-known interventions in Organisational development that are

intended to develop talent and increase employee retention. Through this intervention, employees will be able to improve their skills and socialize leaders in the corporate values to prepare them for strategic leadership roles. In addition, this intervention also focuses on developing skills and knowledge which are necessary for the context of the individual organisation to implement future strategies and to manage the business.

Just like developmental training, this intervention undergoes several processes which are, need assessment, designing the program which starts by stating and clarifying the objectives, implementing, and finally evaluating the program to determine its effectiveness.

Through previous literature reviews, this intervention has shown to improve self-awareness, setting, and achieving goals and working across boundaries in regards to individual trainees' improvements. On the other hand, organisational improvement can be seen in an increased focus on strategy and goal setting and more effective teams. Furthermore, organisational productivity and sales increase, while the turnover rate decreases.

According to Cummings and Worley (2015), Creative work in SMO requires the organisation to build future leaders to understand the implication of changes, and to develop new opportunities and innovative activity. Through this intervention, SCOT will be able to produce leaders who are ready to lead the creative part of the work system.

References:

Active social media users as percentage of the total population in Brunei from 2016 to 2019. (2020). In *Statista*. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/883777/brunei-social-media-penetration/>

Cummings, T. G., & Worley, C. G. (2015). *Organization development and change*. Cengage learning.

Dk Siti Rozaidah Pg Hj Idris ,Haji Kamarul Ridzuan Hj Ismail , (2019), BruTEL's "Going Paperless" Initiative, in Farzana Quoquab , Jihad Mohammad (ed.) Green Behavior and Corporate Social Responsibility in Asia, pp.141 - 146

Five talent management tactics to beat the skills shortage. (2017). In *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesnonprofitcouncil/2017/05/19/five-talent-management-tactics-to-beat-the-skills-shortage/#502c9a531672>

Siti Fatimahwati Pehin Dato Hj Musa, Dk Siti Rozaidah Pg Hj Idris , (2019), Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project, in Farzana Quoquab , Jihad Mohammad (ed.) Green Behavior and Corporate Social Responsibility in Asia, pp.155 - 161

Tannenbaum, S. I., Beard, R. L., & Salas, E. (1992). Team building and its influence on team effectiveness: An examination of conceptual and empirical developments. In *Advances in psychology* (Vol. 82, pp. 117-153). North-Holland.

Wahab , (2019), Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting Ecotourism in the Temburong District, in Farzana Quoquab , Jihad Mohammad (ed.) Green Behavior and Corporate Social Responsibility in Asia, pp.57 - 63

Wilkinson, A., Redman, T., & Dundon, T. (Eds.). (2017). *Contemporary human resource management: text and cases*. London: Pearson.